

D5.1 Health Monitoring Techniques for Chassis Parts

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Executive summary

This report investigates health monitoring techniques for chassis parts. The objectives were focused on selecting optical and acoustic sensors and developing solutions to monitor the damage evolution of real parts under fatigue conditions. To contribute to the improvement of the modelling software for a better correlation with the fatigue simulation has also been within the scope.

Testing has been performed on steel samples as well as samples made of hot-pressed hybrid materials that consist of fiber reinforced plastics with aluminum skins that has been manufactured in the project.

It has been shown that acoustic emission tests can be used to successfully monitor the fatigue damage of metallic specimens. The software developed in this project is capable to acquire and process acoustic emission data and allows to process the data in real time, although the measurements done in this validation have been processed offline. The results obtained show that the use of high pass filters and an adaptative threshold improve the acoustic event detection in fatigue testing conditions. However, there is still work needed to be able to successfully detect acoustic events in noisy environment and to completely validate the processing parameters needed to measure correctly the acoustic events in fatigue testing.

Integration of fiber-optic sensors in FRP hybrid material for health monitoring was demonstrated by embedded sensors in FRP hybrid test specimens exposed to cyclic loading. The concept for embedding sensors was developed and verified. Embedded sensors were monitored during the hot-pressing cycle of the FRP hybrid material. The remaining contraction of the sensor due to thermal and chemical shrinkage could be determined. Embedded fiber-optic sensors could monitor up to 1,5 – 2% strain in quasistatic tensile tests. At low cyclic loading within the linear elastic region the embedded sensors provided strain data for the entire testing cycle, i.e., 18000 cycles at 5 Hz with maximum stress 150 MPa. At high cyclic loading above the linear elastic region the embedded sensors provided strain data for 5000 cycles. Then there was distortion in the signal. The sample failed at 7800 cycles. The sensor was proven intact after failure, it is assumed it was changes in the material and/or the contact to the material surrounding the sensor that failed and caused the distortion. Test parameters were 300 MPa maximum stress at 5 Hz.

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List of abbreviations

<i>AE</i>	<i>Acoustic emission</i>
<i>FBG</i>	<i>Fiber Bragg Grating</i>
<i>FRP</i>	<i>Fiber reinforced plastics</i>
<i>IFSS</i>	<i>Interfacial shear strength</i>
<i>PLB</i>	<i>Pencil Lead Break</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work package</i>

Introduction

The goal of WP5, to which the present deliverable belongs to, is to create and prepare several sensors to track the progression of damage in real parts under fatigue conditions. These sensors will assist the designer in creating a better chassis component and in developing modelling software to increase the correlation between fatigue simulations and the model.

The main objectives of this WP are the following ones:

- To select optical and acoustic sensors and develop solutions to monitor the damage evolution of real parts under fatigue conditions
- To produce a ready solution for damage monitoring
- To contribute to the improvement of the modelling software for a better correlation with the fatigue simulation

To fulfil these objectives, the work package has been divided in three main tasks

- Task 5.1 Select acoustic sensors and develop solutions to monitor the damage evolution of real part under fatigue conditions. Verify technology on test specimen. (EUT)
- Task 5.2 Select optical sensors/surface treatment and develop solutions to monitor the damage evolution of real part under fatigue conditions. Verify technology on test specimens
- Task 5.3 Integration of sensors in FRP- Hybrid material.

1. Acoustic emission sensors for metals

The acoustic emission technique has been used this work to track the progression of damage on fatigue specimens. In this task, the work done is reported and analysed.

1.1 Brief state of the art

According to the *ASTM Guideline of Standard Terminology for Non-destructive Examinations*, acoustic emission is commonly defined as the class of phenomena whereby transient elastic waves are generated by the rapid release of energy from localized sources within a material. This energy dissipation is basically due to phase transformation, crack formation and growth, friction or moving dislocations. Acoustic emission signals may be also generated by such phenomena as leaks, cavitation, solidification and liquefaction.

Research on acoustic emission was launched in the early 1950's and the technological advance in the middle 1960's, mainly in electronic and materials engineering, enabled the rapid development of the method. At present, the acoustic emission technique is applied to many areas of research, both in the civil and industrial field.

The acoustic emission technology is a non-destructive inspection technique that allows both a real time monitoring and a prediction of the behaviour of the studied target. The propagation of the signal recorded in AE is not affected by the structural resonances. In addition, one of the advantages of AE is that it is not necessary an external source to perform the measurement. The basic structure of acoustic emission is as follows [1]:

Figure 1. Block diagram of acoustic emission processing. Adapted from [1]

Since the description of AE sources and the wave propagation sets a lot of unsolved mathematical problems, an exact theory for the characterization of AE does not exist. However, the combination of the outputs of AE experiments and the cognitions about the materials' structure resulted in several empirical and semi-empirical models that give a guideline for the everyday AE practice.

Thresholds are needed for the detection of AE signals. The most used method to evaluate the threshold is the Hsu-Nielsen pencil lead break test. Authors in [2] show that, although this method is widely used to evaluate the sensitivity of the AE sensors, the source generated depends on several factors, as the angle between the pencil and the sample, or the length of the lead.

Figure 2. Pencil break test. Adapted from [2]

To identify evolving AE sources in a signal which contains high AE activity from many different sources, e.g., evolving damages, non-evolving damages, friction, machinery and more, a set of procedures and signal processing methods need to be combined.

According to [3], cumulative of cascade events are the ones that follow the evolution of the temperature in the sample during tensile stress test.

Figure 3. Cascade acoustic emission events vs sample temperature. Adapted from [3]

Cascade events are those that have two or more events in a short time period. The cumulative AE activity can be indicative of the severity of cracking among other behaviours

The use of acoustic emission in fatigue has the added difficulty of the long-time of the test (huge memory needed) and the background noise that gives a very low signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio. To avoid these problems, some studies use tensile tests to evaluate the fatigue behaviour of the material [1].

An example of a low SNR during the measurement occurs when applying acoustic emission to rotating gearboxes. In this case, reference [4] used a floating threshold for transient AE detection. The way to compute this threshold is as follows:

- First, all peak points in the selected time window are detected to obtain the upper envelope of the signal under investigation.
- Then the mean value of the envelope is calculated, which represents the mathematical expectation of the signal amplitude intensity for current time.
- If the signal exceeds the mathematical expectation too much at certain point, closer observation is needed to determine whether or not it is a transient AE event.

- Three times of the standard deviation of the envelope values above the mean value is set as the threshold. In this way, the threshold will dynamically vary depending on the local noise floor.
- All data that are beyond this range are picked out.
- In order to remove the possible false alarm, only those have consecutive spikes over the threshold are considered as a possible AE event rather than outliers.

1.2 Software development

Software development to detect acoustic emission events in fatigue has been one of the most challenging works of this task. The development was needed in order to cope with the following issues:

- **Management of large files.** The previous software used for AE experiments was focused on monotonic tests and fast events. To adapt this software to fatigue experiments, major improvements have been done to deal with large files. This issue forced to work with binary data (TDMS files) and create file partitions. (*i.e., the size of a text file with the data of 4 sensors during 1 second is ~200 MB. For a short fatigue test essay with real demonstrators with a duration of 2 hours: 1.7 TB of data*).
- **High sampling rates.** Sampling rates have been increased up to 2 MHz in order to account for acoustic emission events. Producer-consumer loops have been introduced in the algorithm to be able to capture and store data at these frequency rates.
- **Event detection:** As previously discussed in the SoA section, events in monotonic tests are easily detected, but events in cyclic tests are masked with machine noise and additional methods must be applied. In this case, denoise filters as well as floating thresholds.

Figure 4. Event detected (lower) from a raw signal (upper)

- Real time processing: Acquisition software has been updated to allow real-time processing. Detection methods are implemented and tested offline and online. Validation tests carried out are done offline to maintain all the experimental signal and use the computation.
- Customized interface: Several customized interfaces have been developed to account for all possible measurement configurations (channels, extraction features, etc..). The software used for the acquisition and data processing is done under National instrument LabVIEW® interface.

Figure 5. Software interface developed

Details of the software code are displayed in the Annexes

1.3 Experimental testing

1.3.1 Devices and materials used

For calibration purposes, TWIP steel was tested in a servo-hydraulic testing machine, MTS 322 equipped with a load cell of 250 kN and hydraulic grips. The specimens were loaded at a stress ratio of $R=0.1$. An acoustic emission sensor controlled the integrity of the specimen by detecting the fatigue crack initiation. Additionally, the displacement was recorded to set up the acoustic hits, which could give extra information for the initiation and propagation of a long crack by the end of the test).

Figure 6. Displacement against the number of cycles for a TWIP steel specimen loaded at 735 MPa in a servo-hydraulic machine.

Due to the background noise introduced by the servo-hydraulic machine in the AE sensor, the tests were repeated in a resonance testing machine RUMUL Testronic equipped with a load cell of 150 kN. In this case, the frequency of the test was imposed by the system and recorded as it is a good indicator of a crack initiation. This is explained in detail in section 1.3.3.

Figure 7. Frequency against the number of cycles for a TWIP steel specimen loaded at 735 MPa in a resonance testing machine.

As previously discussed, two different testing machines have been used for the experiments. The main properties of these machines are detailed in the following table:

Table 1: Testing machines used

Testing Machine	Load cell	Test frequency
MTS 322	250 kN	30 Hz
Rumul	150 kN	120 Hz

The hardware used for the acquisition system of AE events is listed below

Table 2: Hardware used for AE data acquisition

Type	Model	Description
DAQ	PCI DAS 4020	Hardware for data acquisition with 4 independent channels and a sampling rate up to 20 MHz
Amplifier	Vallen AEP5	40 dB amplifier for ultrasonic sensor
Sensor	Vallen VS900M	AE sensor with up to 2.4 MHz frequency measurement

1.3.2 Pencil lead break tests

The pencil lead break test (PLB) is a method used in acoustic emission testing to check the acoustic responsiveness between sensor and materials. In this test, a pencil is placed in a fixture

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and then broken by applying a force. The acoustic emission signals generated during the breaking process can be then used to determine material's properties, as the speed of sound, or, as in this case, to as the speed of sound validate the measurement system.

Thus, in this case pencil break tests were performed with the following objectives:

- To check the correct behaviour of all the involved elements.
- To estimate the threshold needed to trigger the measurement.

The tests were done using a 0.5 mm 2H pencil lead with the sample placed in the MTS232 machine.

Figure 8. Pencil break tests machine configuration

During a pencil lead break test, the amplitude of the acoustic emission signals generated can vary depending on a number of factors such as the material being tested, the size and shape of the pencil, and the force applied. Typically, the amplitude of the signals generated during the pencil break test ranges from a few microvolts to a few hundred millivolts.

Figure 9. AE event in time domain (zoomed in lower figure). Measured units of voltage are in mV

In addition, the frequency content of the PLB burst obtained is below 20 kHz, which is a value in accordance with the literature review [1]

Figure 10. Power Spectral density obtained from a pencil break test event

Figure 11. Spectrogram obtained from a pencil break test event sampled at 1 MHz

To summarize, it can be concluded that the results obtained from the pencil lead break tests validate the responsiveness of an AE event detection system (sensors, data acquisition system, signal processing and analysis software).

1.3.3 Event detection tests

Once the elements of the AE detection system are validated, several experiments have been carried out in order to study the detection of AE events using the software developed in this project. In Table 3, a list with the experiments performed is displayed.

Table 3: Acoustic emission experiments

Specimen	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Area [mm ²]	σ_{max} [MPa]	Cycles	Frequency [Hz]	R	Testing machine
TWIP_AE_SP1	9,92	1,44	14,28	735	50970	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP2	9,91	1,43	14,17	741	37458	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP3	9,91	1,42	14,07	746	34496	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP4	9,92	1,45	14,38	730	37090	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP5	9,93	1,45	14,40	729	32791	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP6	9,89	1,44	14,24	737	32891	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP7	9,9	1,45	14,36	731	28266	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP8	9,89	1,44	14,24	737	32891	30	0,1	MTS
TWIP_AE_SP9	9,94	1,45	14,41	729	36100	95	0,1	Rumul
TWIP_AE_SP10	9,93	1,45	14,40	729	29000	97	0,1	Rumul
TWIP_AE_SP11	9,93	1,44	14,30	734	31649	97	0,1	Rumul

All the experiments carried out with MTS machine present a very noisy environment, which posed serious problems when trying to identify AE emission events. The recorded signal has a periodical noise. This noise has very high frequency components and it is possible to still see periodical noise even with a HPF applied.

Figure 12. Wrong acoustic emission event detection. Without filtering (left) and with a HPF applied (right)

In Figure 12 we can see how the periodic noise is maintained even with the high pass filter (HPF) applied.

Instead, in the data obtained with the Rumul machine, the acoustic emission events can be detected with the appropriate filtering and adaptive threshold implemented. The adaptive threshold used in this case is based on the RMS value of the signal. For each segment of data, the RMS is computed. A threshold is then arbitrarily defined and added to this RMS value, and used to detect the AE events.

Figure 13. Qualitative explanation of the adaptative threshold, where RMS is computed for each signal segment and a threshold is added to the resulting value

With this approach, it is possible to isolate events in the Rumul experiments, even if the event data has a low signal to noise ratio in comparison with the environmental noise produced by the test machine.

Figure 14. Correct acoustic emission event detection

1.3.4 Fatigue damage detection

AE techniques are widely used for structural health monitoring. The aim of this project is to apply this technique to monitor the damage during fatigue testing. A large number of signals, including the noises from the load-chain, are detected by the sensitive AE sensors during fatigue testing. Therefore, signal screening methods should be used to filter out the unwanted signals. As previously discussed, in this work, high-pass filters, Teager-Kaiser-Energy Operator TKEO denoise operator and adaptative thresholds are used to detect AE event. Even so, it was not possible to correctly detect the events with the MTS machine experiments, as the noise from the machine masked all the frequency range studied. Thus, in this section only the results obtained with the Rumul machine are analysed.

The data obtained with the AE sensor show significant fluctuation of the amplitude at the beginning of the fatigue test. Thus, this part has been removed from the analysis, and no AE events are counted for the first 50 seconds of signal.

Figure 15. SP11 raw signal data measured

If we look at the results obtained with SP11, it can be observed that with a HPF of 10 kHz, using the TKEO filter and an adaptative threshold of $RMS+2\sigma$, the AE cumulative count (number of times that the amplitude of the signal has exceeded the threshold since the start of the test) seems to provide a good prediction of the crack initiation and crack propagation of the sample (see Figure 16). However, these results are highly dependent on the values used, as the same analysis with a much lower HPF or a lower adaptative threshold gives totally different results. It is worth noticing that the AE system can detect incipient fatigue damage before it is visible on the macroscale. Thus, the method can predict the fracture of a specimen before the crack is visible, leading to more time for replacing the component in a real vehicle.

Figure 16. AE counts (blue) vs frequency measurement for SP11

The power spectral density of the signal shows a peak at the carrier frequency of the testing machine (around 95 Hz), However, most of the frequency content of the signal is found at higher frequencies, between 10 and 1000 kHz.

Figure 17. PSD of a segment of 20 seconds of the SP11 measured signal

A frequency analysis has been carried out filtering the signal with wavelet at different frequencies. The spectrogram of the data at higher frequencies shows different region behaviour. Observing Figure 18, a constant amplitude is detected around 500 kHz. However, this amplitude is lower than the threshold, and the AE event triggered are observed as vertical lines along a wide range of frequencies. However, the analysis of the signal filtered at each frequency band has not provided any significant result and future work is needed in this field.

Figure 18. Spectrogram of a segment of the SP11 signal between 10 kHz and 1000 kHz

A similar analysis is performed for SP9 test using the same processing. However, in this case the results are less conclusive. In the processed data obtained from SP9 test, a significant lower number of AE counts are obtained, and the change of slope of the cumulative value of AE is found at an early stage of the experiment. These results could indicate that not all the AE are being detected by the software. In addition, SP10 could not be processed due to an error when trying to obtain the data from the test machine.

Figure 19. AE counts vs frequency measurement for SP9

2. Embedded sensors in FRP materials

The work in this section includes development and verification of techniques for embedding optical sensors in Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP) and aluminium hybrid materials for structural health monitoring of components subjected to cyclic loading. Challenges are to secure that sensors survive both the manufacturing process of the FRP-Hybrid material and have sufficiently strong bonding to the material matrix when subjected to mechanical loading.

2.1 Methods and results

2.1.1 Selection of fiber-optic sensor type and fiber coating

In this work the Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) [5] sensors have been chosen to detect strain in the FRP-Hybrid material. The reading equipment, the interrogator, launches a broad band pulse into the optical fiber and the FBG reflects the light of a certain wavelength λ_{Bragg} (Fig. 20).

Figure 20. FBG sensing principle and optical fiber.

The reflected wavelength shifts to longer wavelengths when the temperature or strain increases; one degree change in temperature corresponds to 10 pm shift in wavelength, and one μ strain corresponds to 1.2 pm change in wavelength. As the wavelength shift depends both on temperature and strain, the shift corresponding to temperature changes needs to be subtracted from the detected wavelength shift to get the strain. The temperature is detected by another FBG loosely attached on top of the test specimen.

The 125 μ m thick optical fiber has an outer diameter of 150 μ m with Polyimide coating. Polyimide was chosen before acrylate and silicon as fiber coating due to its good adhesion to the silica glass fiber surface, and its thin thickness.

2.1.2 Microbond testing

For quantitative comparison of interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between fibers and resin, Microbond testing has been performed (Fig. 21).

Figure 21. Microbond testing principle to quantify adhesion.

The measurements were done with a high-throughput FIBRObond (Fibrobotics Oy, Tampere, Finland) [6] device. Coated and uncoated optical fibers have been compared to the structural E-glass fibers. The epoxy resin used for testing is identical to the one in the FRP-hybrid material. The results indicate that the adhesion is sufficiently good for both uncoated fibers and the chosen Polyimide coating. For surface mounting of the optical fiber sensors an adhesive has been verified and compared to E-glass. The IFSS results for both the adhesive and resin are shown in (Fig. 22).

Figure 22. IFSS results for Microbond testing results indicating good adhesion to both optical fibers and structural E-glass fibers for the chosen epoxy resin.

2.1.3 Embedding optical sensors in FRP-hybrid material

The manufacturing process for the FRP-hybrid material specimens consists of hot pressing of an E-glass/epoxy pre-preg between two sheets of 0.8 mm aluminium skin plates. The temperature of the tool is 120°C. The optical fiber is embedded with the sensor section centred and aligned in the 0° layer in the pre-preg prior to hot-pressing. Each end of the optical fiber, having connectors mounted, is led out on the side of the specimen. To protect the protruding optical fibers during the hot press cycle, it is necessary to use spacers in the tool. A test specimen with embedded fiber-optic sensor is shown (Fig. 23).

Figure 23. FRP-hybrid material specimen with embedded fiber-optic sensor positioned as the dotted line indicates. The FBG sensor section of the fiber is highlighted in red

3. Integration in FRP-hybrid materials and mechanical testing

The work in this section includes mechanical tests, both static- and fatigue testing, to characterize the performance of integrated/embedded fiber-optic sensors for obtaining strain data for the FRP-hybrid material under both static- and cyclic loading. Comparisons are made both to surface mounted fiber-optic sensors, and to conventional strain measuring techniques i.e., strain gauges and extensometer. Monitoring of strain data has also been conducted during manufacturing of FRP-hybrid test specimens with embedded fiber-optic sensor. The knowledge gathered in WP 2, 3 and 4 has been used to set relevant testing parameters both regarding stress and strain data in static testing and for the cyclic fatigue testing. The methods for embedding and monitoring the fiber-optic sensors described in section 2 have been utilized.

3.1 Methods and results

3.1.1 Manufacturing of FRP-hybrid test specimens with embedded fiber-optic sensors

All test specimens with embedded fiber-optic sensors were manufactured according to the developed method described in 2.1.3. In addition to embedding sensors centred along the length inside the specimens, there were also specimens made with an additional sensor positioned across the test specimen on the opposite side of the FRP-core inside the specimens. The reason for including these sensors was to be able to detect possible increase of temperature inside the specimens during fatigue testing and also possible small contraction of the width while the specimen is extended in the length direction. In Figure 24, a fully equipped test specimen is shown. It has a surface mounted strain gauge and embedded fiber-optic sensors both in vertical and horizontal direction. A variant of test specimens was made with surface mounted fiber-optic sensors in addition to the embedded to investigate if they performed equally as the embedded. Test specimen with surface mounted fiber-optic sensor is shown in figure 25.

The sensor configuration of the different specimens used in the mechanical tests are presented in Table 4.

Figure 24. Test specimen with a surface mounted strain gauge and embedded fiber-optic sensors both in vertical and horizontal directions marked in figure with dotted lines.

Figure 25. Test specimen with both embedded and surface mounted fiber-optic sensors. The surface mounted sensor is aligned with the embedded sensor and centered between the grips of the extensometer.

Table 4: Configuration of sensors in experiments.

Sensors	Quasi-static test		Fatigue test	
	Low load	High load	Low load	High load
Embedded longitudinal FBG	X	X	X	X
Embedded transverse FBG			X	X
Surface mounted longitudinal FBG	X	X		
Extensometer	X			
Strain gauge		X	X	X

3.1.1.1 Monitoring of strain during manufacturing of FRP-hybrid test specimens

Since the pressing cycle for the FRP-hybrid material includes heating to 120°C during compaction, followed by holding at elevated temperature during curing of the FRP core before cooling down to room temperature, it was expected that the embedded fiber-optic sensor would show some remaining strain caused by the pressing cycle. By arranging the pressing of a test specimen so that the sensor could be plugged in to the interrogator and monitored during the

pressing-, curing- and cooling cycle, the resulting change in strain could be determined. As expected, a final remaining compaction of the sensor was detected. The reason for this can be explained by the combination of thermal- and chemical shrinkage caused by the curing occurring at the elevated temperature in the pressing cycle. This effect is not considered to be negative for the performance of the fiber-optic sensor since the remaining compaction measured to be about 1800 micro strain is in the working range for the sensor. It is considered as a positive effect for strain measurements since starting at a compacted stage will increase the measurement range in tension.

In figure 26 the length contraction of the fiber-optic sensor during hot pressing, curing, and cooling is shown. The strain has been determined after compensating for the wavelength shift due to temperature change. The measured remaining contraction at room temperature was determined to be about 1800 micro strain

Figure 26. Diagram showing the length contraction of the fiber-optic sensor during hot pressing, curing and cooling. After cooling the remaining length contraction is about 1800 micro strain.

3.1.2 Comparison of embedded fiber-optic sensors to extensometer and surface mounted fiber-optic sensor in quasi-static testing

A test set-up was made in a MTS model 20 testing machine with a 100 kN load-cell to verify that strain readings from embedded fiber-optic sensors could be logged and be compared to a known reference strain measurement system, i.e. the MTS extensometer. An additional surface mounted fiber was utilized to compare the performance to the embedded sensor. The testing load was limited to be safely within the linear elastic region for the sample. Tests were performed with several repetitions. The result was that both the embedded- and surface mounted optical sensors were detecting the strain similar to the extensometer in the linear elastic region. The test set-up is shown in figure 27.

Figure 27. Test machine MTS during static testing

At low strains up to 0.05% there were some differences noted. One reason can be that the recording of data from the optical sensors are made separately from the testing machine and need to be synchronized in time to match the extensometer connected to the testing machine. This can be an explanation to the horizontal deviation that seems to be in the range of 0.015% between the extensometer and embedded fiber-optic sensor. Most important is that the incline of the curves representing the E-modulus of the test specimen are consistent for the three sensors. In figure 28 strain measurements are shown up to 0.05% strain.

Figure 28. Strain measurements at high resolution up to 0,05% strain indicating that there is some difference in the synchronization to the testing machine but the incline, representing the E-modulus are matching well between the extensometer and the two fiber-optic sensors

3.1.3 Comparison of embedded fiber-optical sensors to strain gauges in quasi-static testing to failure

Tensile testing to failure was performed on a Shimadzu model AG-X plus with a 50 kN load cell. The test set-up is shown in figure 29. The test specimens were equipped with an embedded fiber-optic sensor in the centre and a surface mounted at same location along the specimen. On the opposite side there is a surface mounted strain gauge as reference. The full deformation and damage behaviour of a test specimen is described in figure 30. There is a knee ending the linear elastic region and failure is in the range of 350 MPa. At this stage the composite core in the hybrid material breaks. This is followed by a failure in the aluminium skins at higher strain but lower stress.

Figure 29. Shimadzu, model AG-X plus with a 50 kN load cell during test.

Figure 30. Schematic deformation and damage behavior of a FRP hybrid test specimen is divided in a first failure at about 350 MPa, followed by later failure of the aluminum skins at higher strain.

To check the correlation with tensile data generated on similar FRP hybrid test specimens in WP4, the curve in figure 31 is compared to the stress-strain curve from WP4 shown in figure 32. There is a strong correlation between the curves even though the manufacturing process differs.

Figure 31. The failure of FRP hybrid test sample presented in WP4. This curve shows good correlation with the plotted data in figure 30.

3.1.3.1 Strain to failure data comparing fiber-optic sensors to strain gauges

The results of the strain measurements made both with embedded- and surface mounted fiber-optic sensors are compared to strain data from the surface mounted strain gauges in the figures below where two tests are presented. Overall, it can be concluded that the strain measurements from the optical sensors and strain gauges are matching. The strain gauge survives all the way through the full failure of the aluminium skin plates which is beyond 4% strain. The embedded fiber-optic sensors are in both cases surviving up to between 1,5 - 2% strain, which is in the region of the maximum strain that can be measured according to specifications in data sheets for the fiber-optic sensors. For the surface mounted optical sensors, the measuring works up to about 1% strain in both cases. The fact that the surface mounted optical sensors fails before the embedded sensors is corresponding to the Microbond testing presented above in 2.1.2. Here it is shown that the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) is significantly lower for the epoxy adhesive used for surface mounting than for the epoxy resin used in the FRP hybrid laminate.

In figure 32 strain data for both sample 1 and 2 during tensile tests are shown. They both indicate similar performance for the two sensors in comparison the fiber-optic sensor. The fluctuating response of the surface mounted optical fiber sensor (green) is due to distortions of the wavelength peak that the interrogator uses to calculate the strain. The distortion of the peak comes from a change in strain along the sensor that is assumed originating from changes in the material and/or in the bonding of the sensor to the material.

Figure 32. Strain data for sample 1 and 2. They both indicate that the strain gauges were reading all the way to failure beyond 2% strain. The embedded fiber-optic sensors lasted to between 1,5 - 2% and the surface mounted sensors to about 1% strain.

3.1.4 Comparison of embedded fiber-optic sensors to strain gauges in fatigue testing

The fatigue testing was performed in a hydraulic testing machine, Instron 8516, with a 25 kN load cell. The test set-up is shown in figure 33. The specimens had a surface mounted strain gauge and embedded fiber-optic sensors both in vertical and horizontal directions, corresponding to earlier shown in figure 24.

Figure 33. The test set-up for fatigue testing in a hydraulic Instron 8516 testing machine with a 25 kN load cell. The test specimen has embedded sensors both in vertical and horizontal direction and a surface mounted strain gauge as reference.

Two levels of force were chosen for the fatigue test. The chosen setting in each test is described in table 5. The low level is within the linear elastic region, whereas the high level is above. Fatigue data for the FRP hybrid material from WP4, shown in figure 34, was providing the basis for setting the levels of force.

Table 5: Load settings in fatigue tests

Test name	Maximum stress [MPa]	Frequency [Hz]
Fatigue 1, high	300	5
Fatigue 2, low	150	5

Figure 34. Fatigue data for FRP hybrid material from WP4 was used as input for choosing the two load levels in the test.

During the fatigue test data from both the fiber-optic sensors and the strain gauge were logged separately. The signals from the sensors were also monitored during test. In figure 35 it is shown the type of data that could be followed during the test to secure that the sensors were still functioning and reading strain data properly. The strain gauge data left and the wavelength reading for the optical fibers to the right. While the strain gauge signal is an amplitude to be monitored, the optical fiber signal is a wavelength indicated by a peak cycling its position back and forth horizontally along the wavelength axis. The indication that the test specimen is increasing in length during the test, illustrated by the strain gauge is the slow inclination of the curve pattern where the strain values are increasing over time. For the optical fiber sensor, the fatigue behaviour is instead illustrated by the positions of the min and max values of the wavelength. The cycling interval shown is slowly moving to higher wave lengths (to the right) as the strain levels are increasing during the fatigue testing.

Strain gauge signal

Optical fiber sensor signal

Figure 35. In-situ monitoring of the sensors during the fatigue testing. The slow inclination of the curve for the strain gauges corresponds to a slow increasing of min and max values for the wavelength of the fiber-optic sensors.

3.1.4.1 Comparison of fiber-optic sensors to strain gauges under cyclic loading

The results of data acquisition during cyclic loading from the different sensors are presented below. There are two levels of cycling forces, “Fatigue 1, high” and “Fatigue 2, low” as described in table 5. Since the test specimens are equipped with fiber-optic sensors both in vertical and horizontal direction it is possible to follow changes in strains also across the test specimens. The high load setting in “Fatigue 1” was recorded all the way to failure which occurred after 26 minutes (7800 cycles). The low load setting in “Fatigue 2” was recorded for 1 hour (18 000 cycles) and then terminated without failure.

The peak readings from the vertical optical fiber and the strain gauge for “Fatigue 1, high” is shown in figure 36. As can be seen, the optical fiber signal started to become distorted after about 5000 cycles. It was checked afterwards that the sensor itself was still intact with the same reference readings as before the test. The distortion is then suggested coming from uneven stress distribution along the length of the sensor due to some possible changes in the material surrounding the embedded sensor. In figure 18 the readings from the transverse fiber-optic sensor are shown. The observation that the strain readings are increasing over time in the vertical direction while they are decreasing in the transverse direction could possibly indicate that the test specimen is increasing in length and narrows in width during the test.

The peak readings from the vertical optical fiber and the strain gauge for “Fatigue 2, low” is shown in figure 19 and in figure 20 the readings from the transverse fiber-optic sensor are shown. Here at lower force the inclination of the strain curve is lower but still detectable.

Figure 36. The peak readings from the vertical optical fiber and the strain gauge for “Fatigue 1, high”. The optical fiber signal started to become distorted after about 5000 cycles. The inserts show the peak before and after 5000 cycles

Figure 37. The peak readings from the horizontal optical fiber for “Fatigue 1, high”.

Figure 38. The peak readings from the vertical optical fiber and the strain gauge for “Fatigue 2, low”.

Figure 39. The peak readings from the horizontal optical fiber for “Fatigue 2, low”.

4. Conclusions

4.1 Conclusions, Acoustic emission for metals

- Acoustic emission tests can be used to successfully monitor the fatigue damage of metallic specimens. However, the results are highly sensitive to the input parameters needed to process the data (frequency cut-off, threshold value, etc.).
- The software developed in this project is capable to acquire and process acoustic emission data. This software allows to process the data in real time, although the measurements done in this validation have been processed offline.
- The pencil lead break test has been successfully applied to validate all the components of the acoustic emission measuring system.
- The use of filters and adaptive threshold improve the acoustic event detection in fatigue testing conditions, however the use of these parameters has only been validated for two experimental fatigue tests. More tests are needed to prove the robustness of the method used.
- Frequency analysis is done using wavelet decomposition, proving that AE events have a wide spectrum of frequencies. Still, no significant information is found when analysing the frequency bands and a deeper analysis would be needed.

4.2 Conclusions, Embedded sensors in FRP hybrid material

- Microbond testing is proven an effective method to verify adhesion on fiber-optic sensors for both adhesives and thermoset resins.
- Concept for embedding fiber-optic sensors in FRP hybrid materials was developed and verified.

4.3 Conclusions, Integration in FRP hybrid material and mechanical testing

- Integration of fiber-optical sensors in FRP hybrid material for health monitoring was demonstrated by embedded sensors in FRP hybrid test specimens exposed to cyclic loading.
- Embedded sensors were monitored during the hot-pressing cycle of the FRP hybrid material. The remaining contraction of the sensor due to thermal- and chemical shrinkage could be determined.
- Embedded fiber-optic sensors could monitor up to 1,5 – 2% strain in quasistatic tensile tests.
- At low cyclic loading within the linear elastic region the embedded sensors provided strain data for the entire testing cycle.
- At high cyclic loading above the linear elastic region the embedded sensors provided strain data for 5000 cycles. Then there was distortion in the signal. The sample failed at 7800 cycles. The sensor was proven intact after failure, it is assumed it was changes in the material and/or the contact to the material surrounding the sensor that failed and caused the distortion. Test parameters were 300 MPa maximum stress at 5 Hz.

5. REFERENCES

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6. ANNEXES

6.1 Annex A: Acquisition software code

The acquisition software is composed of several modules

Input channel setup

The data samples acquisition is obtained using the ULx library that comes with the Measurement Computing hardware used in this project. The library is task-based, and several blocks are used to define each data channel, impose the sample clock and start the measurement

Figure 40. ULx module acquisition

Producer loop

In the producer loop, a trigger is used to detect if an AE event has occurred. When the trigger is activated, a batch of samples are recorded and sent to the producer loop

Figure 41. Basic Trigger module

An adaptative threshold can also be used for the trigger. This threshold can be changes according to the RMS of the signal obtained, or using a Hilbert envelope

Figure 42 Adaptive Trigger module

Consumer loop

The consumer loop can be used to display and store all the data (offline method) or only the data of the events triggered (online method)

Figure 43 Consumer loop